

NEW QUALITATIVE EVALUATION CRITERIA TRAINING PROGRAM

SuHAMK CoARAb Project

Abstract

This document contains the training program for using the new qualitative evaluation criteria at Häme University of Applied Sciences. This training program is primarily used for recruiting and evaluating Principal Research Scientists but can also be applied to other researchers.

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Introduction

SuHAMK CoARAb Project

This document has been created as part of the SuHAMK CoARAb project at Häme University of Applied Sciences. The SuHAMK CoARAb project is part of the CoARA Cascade Boost Funding and funded by the European Union.

This 1-year EU funded project aims to develop new effective qualitative researcher evaluation criteria which will be mapped into HAMK's existing principal research scientist evaluation processes. The new qualitative researcher evaluation criteria support the recognition of diverse researcher skills and different researcher career paths, enhances HAMK's research quality and promotes transparency and accountability in the researcher evaluation processes. Strong collaboration with HAMK's principal research scientists, principal research scientist supervisors, the researcher evaluation team and other relevant HAMK personnel have helped identify the new qualitative evaluation criteria in this document. A new sustainable evaluation framework will be developed around these new criteria and comprehensive training on their active utilization will be provided to relevant HAMK personnel.

Training Program

This training program has been designed to help relevant personnel utilize the new qualitative evaluation criteria during the evaluation of principal research scientists. This training program has been designed for the recruitment process and for the tenure track evaluation process.

Not all the new qualitative evaluation criteria has been included in this training program and can be found in a separate document '*the new qualitative evaluation criteria.*' This training program has been designed to introduce the new qualitative evaluation criteria to relevant and new personnel and provide guidelines for how to adopt them in recruitment and evaluation processes.

Contents

This training program contains training guidelines and materials for:

- **Recruitment of new Principal Research Scientists**
 - Stage 1
 - Stage 2

- **The tenure track evaluation of Principal Research Scientists**
 - 1st Evaluation
 - 2nd Evaluation
 - 3rd Evaluation

Recruitment Process

The diagram below represents the newly proposed recruitment process. This new recruitment process has been designed to help support the consideration of qualitative evaluation criteria in the Principal Research Scientist assessment. Proposed tools have also been provided and can be found in **Annex 1**.

Recruitment Guidelines

Stage 1

During the recruitment process, applicants will be asked to submit a range of documents. The newly proposed recruitment process proposes that during the 1st round of recruitment applicants will be asked to submit a **modified HAMK TENK CV, List of Publications, Research Plan**, and a **motivational letter**. These can all be found in **Annex 1**.

Below is a set of potential qualitative evaluation criteria for assessing the applicant's documents. Some criteria may appear in multiple documents. Evaluators should use only the most relevant criteria based on the job description and the documents submitted.

Publication List

Peer-Reviewed Publications	
Criteria	Description
Variation of role in authorship (1 st author, 2 nd author, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see varying roles in authorship. ➤ For early career researchers it is understandable to see more 1st author roles. ➤ For more senior career researchers it is important to see more 2nd, 3rd etc. authorship roles. ➤ Variation of authorship roles suggests flexibility in ideas, teamwork and collaboration skills.
Open access publishing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see peer-reviewed articles being published in open access journals. ➤ Open access is promoted but understanding and caution for limitations in being able to publish in open access journals and the relatively 'recent' promotion of open access needs to be considered. ➤ Open access publishing reflects better 'research impact' and research dissemination, and similar 'open access' values.
Variation in transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary and specialization of published research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see a variation in both specialization and transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary publishing. ➤ The ability to publish with both field specialization and trans-, inter-, multidisciplinary approaches suggests innovative flexibility and reflects the values and research strategy of HAMK.
Variation of publication collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see a variation in authorship collaborations. ➤ The ability to publish with a variety of different authors and researchers reflects collaboration and teamwork skills, innovative flexibility.

<p>Variation of both sole authorship and multiple authorship publications</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable to see that researchers are capable of publishing both sole and multiple author articles. ➤ For early career researchers it is understandable to see more sole authored articles. ➤ For more senior career researchers it is important to see collaboration with other authors. ➤ The ability to publish as a single author and as part of a group of authors reflects collaboration and teamwork skills, communication skills and innovative flexibility.
<p>Collaboration within international authorship groups</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable to see that researchers are capable of publishing both sole and multiple author articles. ➤ For early career researchers it is understandable to see more sole authored articles. ➤ For more senior career researchers it is important to see collaboration with other authors. ➤ The ability to publish within international authorship groups reflects collaboration and teamwork skills, communication skills, innovative flexibility and expands potential research impact.

<p>Activeness In Field (up to date and active with relevant networks and events)</p>	
<p>Criteria</p>	<p>Description</p>
<p>Activeness in publication and authorship</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable to see continued activity in submitting, applying or participating in funding applications. ➤ Continued activeness demonstrates up to date understanding of research, debates, perspectives and academic trends. ➤ However, it is important to consider career breaks, career stages and employment in other professions. ➤ Recent experience is important.

Modified HAMK TENK CV

<p>Relevant Research Experience</p>	
<p>Criteria</p>	<p>Description</p>
<p>Practical experience in research field</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Important to recognise other relevant research related employment, roles or duties. ➤ Other relevant work experience where research has been conducted needs to be considered.

Experience in Applied Research

Criteria	Description
Variation of different development project collaborations (especially involving the business industry).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable to see that researchers have been involved in various development projects. ➤ The career stage of the researcher needs to be considered. More variation is desirable in more senior researcher career stages. ➤ Development projects within the business industry are prioritized.
Variation of role and contribution in different development projects (especially involving the business industry).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see that researchers have experience in different roles in development projects. ➤ The career stage of the researcher needs to be considered. More variation is desirable in more senior researcher career stages. ➤ Different roles reflect flexibility, teamworking and collaboration skills. ➤ Development projects within the business industry are prioritized.
Variation of stakeholders in development projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see variation in different types of stakeholders used and incorporated into development projects. ➤ A variation of stakeholders reflects skills in stakeholder inclusion, communication, teamwork and collaboration, and innovative flexibility.
Transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary approach (use of multiple researchers, disciplines, partners etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see that researchers have applied or have experience in being involved in transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary development projects. ➤ Here it is also important to consider lessons learnt. If transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary approaches have not been used or incorporated effectively, the researcher's acknowledgement of this is also valuable.

Funding Applications

Criteria	Description
Variation of role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see variation of roles in funding applications, ➤ Variation role reflects skills in teamwork and collaboration, communication and suggests researchers have a holistic understanding of the funding application process. ➤ Unsuccessful applications can be included.
Variation of funding sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see a variation of different funding sources applied to. ➤ The career stage of the researcher needs to be considered. More senior researchers are more likely to have a wider variation in sources.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Variation in funding sources. ➤ Unsuccessful applications can be included.
Quality of funding applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Reviewers feedback, score, placement etc. can be examined for both unsuccessful and successful funding applications.
Variation of funding application collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have experience in different funding application collaborations. ➤ Variation in collaboration in terms of size and variation in collaborators (international, discipline etc.), reflects innovative flexibility, communication skills, teamwork and collaboration skills. ➤ These details can be examined by discussing the previous funding application experiences of researchers.

Collaboration Skills

Criteria	Description
Variation of authorship collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Researchers' ability to collaborate with a variety of authors including from different research fields or industries, different nationalities, different perspectives can demonstrate flexibility. ➤ Here variation is important. ➤ The researcher career stage should be considered. Variety is important for more senior researchers.
Variation of authorship role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see varying roles in authorship as this reflects ability, in being able to collaborate in different team roles and having teamwork skills.
Variation of trans-, inter-, multidisciplinary collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ A variation of collaboration in trans-, inter-, multidisciplinary approaches demonstrates flexibility in working with different perspectives, researchers, disciplines and applying different approaches.
Variation of role in development projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see varying roles in development projects, this reflects being able to collaborate in different team roles and having teamwork skills. ➤ A prioritisation is given to experience in/with the business industry.
Variation of development project stakeholder and/or partner collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Researchers' ability to collaborate with various stakeholders or other partners demonstrates innovative flexibility and teamwork skills as they can work with different industries and able to incorporate different ideas and needs. ➤ A prioritisation is given to experience in/with the business industry.

Problem-Solving Skills

Criteria	Description
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<p>Experience working in development projects (or other professional roles) which have solved stakeholder problems.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see that researchers have experience with working on development projects (or other professional roles) which incorporate problem solving duties for stakeholders. ➤ A prioritisation is given to experience in/with the business industry.
<p>Variation of stakeholders in development projects</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see that researchers can solve problems and provide solutions for different stakeholders, with varying scenarios, needs and perspectives. ➤ A prioritisation is given to experience in/with the business industry.

Activeness In Field	
Criteria	Description
<p>Activeness in development projects</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable to see continued activity in conducting or participating in development projects. ➤ Continued activeness demonstrates up to date understanding of stakeholder needs and issues. ➤ However, it is important to consider career breaks, career stages and employment in other professions. ➤ Recent experience is important. ➤ A prioritisation is given to experience in/with the business industry.
<p>Activeness in funding applications</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable to see continued activity in submitting, applying or participating in funding applications. ➤ Continued activeness demonstrates motivation to seek funding and innovate new research and/project ideas. ➤ However, it is important to consider career breaks, career stages and employment in other professions. ➤ Recent experience is important.
<p>Activeness in publication and authorship</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable to see continued activity in submitting, applying or participating in funding applications. ➤ Continued activeness demonstrates up to date understanding of research, debates, perspectives and academic trends. ➤ However, it is important to consider career breaks, career stages and employment in other professions. ➤ Recent experience is important.
<p>Activeness in relevant events and networks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable to see continued activity in researcher attending networking events, webinars, conferences, discussions etc. ➤ This reflects up to date awareness of relevant issues, networks, challenges, opportunities and findings in the field.

Pedagogical Communication Skills	
Criteria	Description
Preparation of educational materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see that researchers have experience in developing educational materials. ➤ The importance of this skill is highly dependent on the role and duties of the researchers. ➤ Being able to develop and prepare educational materials reflect pedagogical skills but also communication skills.
Experience in facilitation activities and/roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ If researchers are expected to conduct teaching, having experience in facilitating activities or having facilitation roles reflects communication skills which support being able to manage group settings. ➤ Such experience is also important for researchers in stakeholder facilitation situations.
Experience in teaching activities and/roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ If researchers are expected to conduct teaching, having experience in teaching and/or have pedagogical qualifications and training is important.
Variation in teaching, and/or facilitation audiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Experience in teaching and facilitating a variation of audiences reflects adaptive communication skills and knowledge of being able to teach and manage different groups and/or individuals. ➤ Desirable to see that researchers have experience in teaching different types of audiences.

Pedagogical Collaboration	
Criteria	Description
Experience designing and developing study units with other researchers and/or lectures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable to see that researchers have experience in developing study units as this reflects the ability to collaborate with other researchers and/or lecturers to develop pedagogical material. ➤ This reflects the ability of the researcher to collaborate at a pedagogical level.
Experience in pedagogical collaboration projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable to see that researchers have been involved in development projects which focus on pedagogical institutions, stakeholders, tools, etc. ➤ This skill may only be relevant to researchers in specific fields where development projects with a pedagogical aspect is required.
Collaboration with educational professionals, lecturers, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ If researchers have experience collaborating with educational professional, it reflects communication and collaboration skills which is needed for those institutions and stakeholders.

<p>Integrating study units into research and/or development projects</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable that researchers have had previous experience in utilising or incorporating study units into research and/or development projects. ➤ This may include using students in the research and/or project, presenting research and/or project outputs etc. in courses, using students to help develop or test ideas and solutions etc. ➤ This can also be discussed with the researcher on their current research proposal, how they plan to consider or integrate study units and courses into their research.
<p>Development of learning methods and tools</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable that researchers have experience in actively developing learning methods or tools. ➤ This may include contributing to workshops, brainstorming sessions, participation in relevant development projects, being a specific duty or role, etc.
<p>Development of teaching</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable that researchers have experience in actively developing teaching methods. ➤ This may include contributing to workshops, brainstorming sessions, participation in relevant development projects, being a specific duty or role, etc.

Peer Recognition in Pedagogical Field

Criteria	Description
<p>Awards or nominations related to teaching and/or pedagogical achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Awards, nominations etc., which have been recognized by peers in the pedagogical field are very significant. ➤ This will only be relevant for those researchers who have a significant amount of teaching duties and/or activities. ➤ The career stage of the researcher needs to also be considered. Peer recognition will most likely accumulate alongside the length of the researcher's career.
<p>Invitations or experience as guest lecturer, speaker etc. at events related to pedagogy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see researchers have been invited to pedagogical events, seminars, lectures as guest speakers etc. ➤ This reflects that the researcher is known in the pedagogical field and is respected.
<p>Invitation to attend media, workshops, webinars etc. related to pedagogy as an expert</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see researchers have been invited to act as an 'expert' in the field of pedagogy in media, webinars, seminars etc. events, seminars, lectures as guest speakers etc. ➤ This reflects that the researcher is known in the pedagogical field and is respected.

Peer Recognition in Pedagogical Field	
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Leadership Skills and Experience	
Criteria	Description
Experience in leadership roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have experience in leadership roles. ➤ This can include roles related to research and/or development projects but other experience in other duties and professions is also acknowledged.
Participation in leadership courses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ If researchers do not have active leadership experience, training courses are desirable to see, ➤ Here, all courses and training in leadership are important but especially for those who do not have as much leadership experience.

Peer Impact Skills	
Criteria	Description
Experience in providing peer review, on research,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable for researchers to have experience in providing feedback on their own peers through different activities and duties.

funding applications, projects etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ This can include roles related to research and/or development projects but other experience in other duties and professions is also acknowledged
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Mentoring, Facilitation and Supervision Skills	
Criteria	Description
Experience in mentoring, facilitating and/or supervision roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable for researchers to have experience in mentoring, facilitating and/or supervision roles. This can include duties and roles outside of research and/or development projects. ➤ Mentoring, facilitation and supervisions roles can include a range of activities and duties. Student thesis supervision, workshop facilitation, training other researchers etc.

Communication & Dissemination Skills	
Criteria	Description
Extent of research dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have experience in sharing research results. ➤ This includes research being shared in events, conferences, webinars, blogs, social media etc. ➤ Important for researchers to be aware of appropriate platforms where research can be disseminated. ➤ This can be examined in the research proposal or ask the researcher to explain their research dissemination choices and experience in previous research. ➤ This criterion reflects wider dissemination skills, academic communication skills, and networking skills.
Variation of communication platforms used	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have experience using multiple different platforms when communicating and/or disseminating research. ➤ Variation in communication platforms which also target different audiences is desirable. ➤ Here it is important to see that researchers are familiar with different forms of dissemination platforms and when to utilise them. ➤ Knowledge and use of platforms relevant to the business industry is especially important.
Variation of languages used	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Communication which has been produced in more than one language suggests wider outreach. ➤ It would be especially important for materials to be produced in the local language to reach local audiences and stakeholders.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It would also be important for communication to be produced in English as this allows for international outreach.
Variation of target audiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have experiences in communicating with or to a variation of audiences. ➤ Being able to verbally and non-verbally communicate with different industry official, policymakers, students and citizens is very valuable and supports open access of research and wider social impact opportunities. ➤ This also includes producing and adapting materials and speeches to relate to different audiences. ➤ Communication with a variation of business industry stakeholders is particularly important.
Open access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Communication which supports open access principles is also important. ➤ Whilst this may be difficult to assess, publishing with open access in mind, translating research or information into local languages, creating free and accessible material, presenting at open events, adapting language style to communicate with different audiences can all be used to support open access.
Variation of mediums used to present research and data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have experience in producing different materials to communicate research outputs. ➤ This may include presentations, short blogs, one pager, social media posts, diagrams, graphs etc. ➤ The research field needs to be considered as this criterion may be more relevant or applicable in certain fields.
Preparation of marketing and pitching material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have experience in producing or contributing to marketing and pitching materials. ➤ Being able to effectively pitch research ideas to business industry stakeholders is an important aspect in HAMK.
Variation of development project stakeholder and/or partner collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Researchers' ability to collaborate with various stakeholders or other partners demonstrates flexibility in working with different industries and being able to incorporate different ideas and needs. ➤ A prioritisation is given to experience in/with the business industry.

Recognition in Industry and/or Field

Criteria	Description
Awards, nominations, special mentions etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Awards, nominations and special mentions in research and or in relevant industry are recognized.

<p>Guest speaker invitations to events, conferences, webinars,</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to be recognized in their relevant research field and/or industry. ➤ Invitations to act as guest speakers or specialists at events, conferences, debates, media etc.
<p>Specialist or expert job titles in the business industry field</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Specialist job titles and roles in other relevant professions can also be acknowledged.

Networking Skills

Criteria	Description
<p>Extent of existing networks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Existing networks in the business industry, academic institutions, government and civil society are all recognized. ➤ This can be examined through current memberships and activities in different events, networks, discussions etc. ➤ Collaboration in projects, with stakeholders, policymakers, educators etc. can also be recognized. ➤ Networks in the business industry are particularly important.
<p>Experience in networking roles</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have active networking experience. ➤ This can also be recognized in other professions or duties outside of research and project implementation.
<p>Experience in face-to-face networking</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have experience in networking at live events as this requires different communication and networking skills in comparison to virtual events. ➤ This can be examined through their 'live' attendance at conferences, events, debates, and other networking events.
<p>Ability to recognize appropriate networks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable for researchers to be aware or knowledgeable of appropriate networks on their research and/development projects. ➤ This can be primarily examined when discussing the researcher's research proposal.

Teamwork and Collaboration Skills

Criteria	Description
<p>Variation of development project, stakeholder and/or partner collaborations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Researchers' ability to collaborate with various stakeholders or other partners demonstrates flexibility in working with different industries and being able to incorporate different ideas and needs. ➤ Prioritization is given to experience in/with the business industry.

<p>Demonstrated teamwork experience</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have experience in teamwork. ➤ Teamwork experience in other professions and roles outside of research and/or development projects are also acknowledged.
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Research Plan Proposal

<h3>Relevant Research Experience</h3>	
<p>Consideration of regional, national, and/or international strategies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to be able to connect and apply their research to regional, national and/or international strategies and issues. ➤ This can be examined in the research proposal or ask the researcher to explain their use of regional, national, and/or international strategies in their previous research.
<p>Suitability with HAMK strategy and/or education units</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to be able to consider the integration of their current research or previously conducted research with HAMK’s research strategy and/or study units. ➤ This can be examined in the research proposal or ask the researcher to explain their consideration of research and education integration in their previous research.
<p>Competence in funding applications, planning and strategy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to be able to recognise their role in needing to secure funding and be able to recognise appropriate funding sources. ➤ This can be examined in the research proposal or ask the researcher to explain their strategy for securing funding in their research proposal or discuss previous funding application experiences. ➤ Here it is also important to consider lessons learnt. If funding source recognition and/or application has not been successful in current or previous research, the researcher’s acknowledgement of this also positively supports this criterion.

<h3>Understanding of Research Impact</h3>	
Criteria	Description
<p>Ability to recognize appropriate tools, theoretical frameworks, analysis methods etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable to see that applicants can recognize and justify the use of appropriate tools, theoretical frameworks, analysis methods etc. when conducting research. ➤ This can be examined in the research proposal or ask the researcher to explain their use of the above-mentioned in their previous research. ➤ Here it is also important to consider lessons learnt. If tools, theoretical frameworks, analysis methods

	<p>have not been effectively or successfully incorporated into previous research, the researcher’s acknowledgement of this also positively supports this criterion.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Also good to ask and/or discuss negative or unsuccessful experiences.
<p>Extent of research dissemination in research related and/or academic circles</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable for researchers to have experience in sharing research results in relevant academic circles and networks. ➤ This includes research being shared in events, conferences, webinars, blogs etc. ➤ It is important for researchers to be aware of appropriate platforms where research can be disseminated. ➤ This can be examined in the research proposal or ask the researcher to explain their research dissemination choices and experience in previous research. ➤ This criterion reflects wider dissemination skills, academic communication skills, and networking skills.
<p>Use of transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary approaches</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary research experience. ➤ This can be examined in the research proposal or ask the researcher to explain their use of research transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary approaches and experience in previous research. ➤ Here it is also important to consider lessons learnt. If transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary approaches have not been used or incorporated effectively into previous research, the researcher’s acknowledgement of this is also valuable.
<p>Application of research findings e.g. policy proposals, legislation, corporate procedures etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable for research to have been actively incorporated or having influenced real processes. ➤ Here it is important to consider the research field itself and how plausible this is given the different circumstances and context of different research fields.

Wider Social Impact	
Criteria	Description
<p>Consideration of regional, national, and/or international strategies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the current completed research or the previously completed research. ➤ The application or consideration for regional, national and/international strategies and/or objectives reflects that the research has been completed with a wider impact in mind.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable for researchers to be able to consider the integration of their current research or previously

<p>Consideration of HAMK research strategy, study units and/or courses in research plan</p>	<p>conducted research with HAMK’s research strategy and/or study units.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ This can be examined in the research proposal or ask the researcher to explain their consideration of research and education integration in their previous research.
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<p>Networking Skills</p>	
<p>Criteria</p>	<p>Description</p>
<p>Ability to recognize appropriate networks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable for researchers to be aware or knowledgeable of appropriate networks on their research and/development projects. ➤ This can be primarily examined when discussing the researcher’s research proposal.

Stage 2

After the first stage of applicant evaluation is complete, the applicants chosen will proceed to stage 2 of the recruitment process. These applicants will be invited to an interview.

Before the interview each applicant will be provided with the following:

- **Ideal Research Proposal Instructions:**
 - Applicants will be asked to describe and explain their ideal research proposal. This exercise is purely imaginary but helps to highlight applicants’ innovative motivations and skills. The applicants will receive a template for this ideal research proposal prior to the interview.
- **Research Plan Presentation Template and Instructions:**
 - Applicants will be asked to conduct a 10-minute research plan presentation at the interview. A template and instructions for the presentations, including important focus points, will be provided to the applicants prior to the interview.
- **Pre-Interview Preparation Template:**
 - Prior to the interview applicants will be asked to fill in a pre-interview preparation template in which here the applicant is asked to provide details of their achievements, contributions, skills, added value etc. After being completed this document will be sent to the interviewers prior to the interview and will be used as a foundation for the interview itself.

At the interview applicants will be asked to present their **ideal research proposal** and conduct a 10-minute **research proposal presentation**. The interviewers will also ask questions from the applicant based upon the **pre-interview preparation template** and any other relevant **free form questions**. All these documents can be found in **Annex 2**.

Below is a set of potential qualitative evaluation criteria for assessing the applicant’s pre-interview documents and the applicant during the interview process. Some criteria can be

used for more than one document and/or presentation. Evaluators should use only the most relevant criteria based on the job description and the documents submitted.

Ideal Research Proposal

Relevant Research Experience	
<p>Ability to recognize appropriate tools, theoretical frameworks, analysis methods etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see that applicant can recognise and justify the use of appropriate tools, theoretical frameworks, analysis methods etc. when conducting research. ➤ This can be examined in the research proposal or ask the researcher to explain their use of the above mentioned in their previous research. ➤ Here it is also important to consider lessons learnt. If tools, theoretical frameworks, analysis methods have not been effectively or successfully incorporated into previous research, the researcher's acknowledgement of this also positively supports this criterion. ➤ Also good to ask and/or discuss negative or unsuccessful experiences.
<p>Consideration and recognition for research ethics</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see acknowledgement of research ethics in current research proposal and in previous research. ➤ This can be examined in the research proposal or ask the researcher to explain their use of ethics in their previous research. ➤ Here it is also important to consider lessons learnt. If ethics have not been effectively or successfully incorporated into previous research, the researcher's acknowledgement of this also positively supports this criterion. ➤ Also good to ask and/or discuss negative or unsuccessful experiences.

Research Plan Presentation

Networking Skills	
Criteria	Description
<p>Ability to recognize appropriate networks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable for researchers to be aware or knowledgeable of appropriate networks on their research and/development projects. ➤ This can be primarily examined when discussing the researcher's research proposal.

Adoption of Open Science Practices

At HAMK the utilisation of the criteria below, will most likely occur during the tenure track evaluation process. However, the below mentioned criteria can also be applied and identified when examining previous or proposed research.

Criteria	Description
Open access publication and research dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to recognize the importance of publishing and disseminating research and project outputs openly. ➤ This can be examined by discussing previous, current or future ideas for research and how open access publication has been considered or incorporated. ➤ The research field and nature of research needs to be considered. If open access principles cannot be adhered to, justification for this is equally important.
Open data sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is important for researchers to recognize the importance of open access principles such as open data sharing. ➤ This can be examined by discussing previous, current or future ideas for research and how open data sharing has been considered or incorporated. ➤ The research field and nature of research needs to be considered. If open access principles cannot be adhered to, justification for this is equally important.
Open methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is important for researchers to recognize the importance of open access principles such as open methods sharing. ➤ This can be examined by discussing previous, current or future ideas for research and how open method sharing has been considered or incorporated. ➤ The research field and nature of research needs to be considered. If open access principles cannot be adhered to, justification for this is equally important.
Sharing with society members and businesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is important for researchers to acknowledge that research and project outputs and general information should be effectively shared with relevant stakeholders and society at large. ➤ It is important for researchers to understand the importance of ordinary citizens being aware of research and being able to benefit from it. ➤ This can be examined by discussing previous, current or future ideas for research and how awareness of other relevant stakeholders and ordinary citizens has been considered or incorporated. ➤ The research field and nature of research needs to be considered. If open access principles cannot be adhered to, justification for this is equally important.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable for researchers to understand the importance of creating educational materials which can be used at HAMK and disseminated to other relevant stakeholders and ordinary citizens.

<p>Open educational resources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ This can be examined by discussing previous, current or future ideas for research where educational materials have been produced or will be produced. ➤ Open access and open sharing of educational materials can be discussed. ➤ This may only be relevant to certain researchers from certain research fields. ➤ The research field and nature of research needs to be considered. If open access principles cannot be adhered to, justification for this is equally important.
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Effective Completion of Research

At HAMK the utilisation of the criteria below, will most likely occur during the tenure track evaluation process. However, the below mentioned criteria can also be applied and identified when examining previous or proposed research.

Criteria	Description
<p>Objectives and aims achieved or shortcoming acknowledged</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The objectives and aims should be clearly defined and the way they will be achieved and measured. ➤ The successful completion of these aims and objectives can be assessed. ➤ It is important to also consider the 'failure' to achieve the initial outlined aims and objectives, when the researcher can identify the challenges, issues and lessons learnt. ➤ The ability of the researcher to acknowledge short coming and plan for their avoidance in the future is also a vital skill.
<p>Time management</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ An initial timeline should be outlined in the research proposal and further discussed during the tenure track. ➤ The ability of the research to adhere to the timeline or be able to justify or acknowledge changes to the timeline should be assessed. ➤ Justified amendments to the timeline in reaction to changes or unforeseen circumstances reflect problem-solving skills and should be acknowledged in the assessment.
<p>Ability to recognize appropriate tools, theoretical frameworks, analysis methods etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable to see that applicants can recognize and justify the use of appropriate tools, theoretical frameworks, analysis methods etc. when conducting research. ➤ Here it is also important to consider lessons learnt. If tools, theoretical frameworks, analysis methods have not been effectively or successfully incorporated into previous research, the researcher's acknowledgement of this also positively supports this criterion. ➤ Also good to ask and/or discuss negative or unsuccessful experiences.

<p>Consideration and recognition for research ethics</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the current completed research or the previously completed research. ➤ The application or consideration for ethics in the research where choices are justified, shortcomings acknowledged, lessons learnt indicate competence in completing quality research.
<p>Consideration of regional, national, and/or international strategies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the current completed research or the previously completed research. ➤ The application or consideration for regional, national and/international strategies and/or objectives reflects that the research has been completed with a wider impact in mind.
<p>Consideration of integration with education</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the current completed research or the previously completed research. ➤ The application or consideration for integrating the research results or research implementation into educational purposes reflects that the research has been completed with wider impact in mind.

Pre-Interview Preparation Document Overview

<p>Problem-Solving Skills</p>	
<p>Stakeholder benefit of research and/or project</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see that researchers have been able to successfully provide solution which benefit stakeholders. ➤ This can be reflected in stakeholders adopting project proposals and/or developed services, projects etc, positive stakeholder feedback, multiple and/or extended collaboration with the same stakeholders. ➤ A prioritisation is given to experience in/with the business industry.
<p>Practical adoption of research, knowledge, service etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Like the above, it is desirable to see that development projects have had practical benefits to stakeholders and/or to the wider public. ➤ Development project outputs have been adopted by the direct stakeholders and/or the wider public. ➤ This reflects being able to problem solve not only for the direct stakeholder but also for the wider project.
<p>Extent of face-to-face stakeholder interaction.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have experience in live or face-to-face interaction with stakeholders. ➤ The type of interaction may vary. Being present 'live' at business meetings, board meetings, conferences, events, debates etc. ➤ Here experience in face-to-face interaction with business industry stakeholders is especially important. ➤ Face-to-face interaction also supports effective networking skills.

Leadership Skills and Experience

Criteria	Description
Experience in leadership roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have experience in leadership roles. ➤ This can include roles related to research and/or development projects but other experience in other duties and professions is also acknowledged.
Demonstrates similar leadership values and understanding of duties as organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to portray similar leadership values as HAMK. ➤ It is important for the researcher to have a clear understanding that they will be leading a research group, and this requires the researcher to strive for the success of the research group as opposed to only their own individual success and development.

Similar Values to Organization

Criteria	Description
Demonstrates willingness to incorporate trans-, inter-, and multidisciplinary approaches and recognizes their importance,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to be willing, motivated and flexible enough to incorporate transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary approach, ➤ This can be examined when discussing the researchers current and/or previous research and to what extent they have or plan to incorporate transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary approach. ➤ It is important to consider the role of specialization in certain fields, but there should be willingness to consider transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary approaches.
Demonstrates similar teamwork values and expected duties as organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable for researchers to portray similar teamwork values as HAMK. ➤ Desirable for researchers to understand the importance of teamwork in their respective research groups and the centrality placed on teamwork with stakeholders, project partners, other researchers etc. ➤ It is important for researchers to understand that they will not be conducting research alone.
Demonstrates similar leadership values and understanding of expected duties as organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable for researchers to portray similar leadership values as HAMK. ➤ It is important for the researcher to have a clear understanding that they will be leading a research group, and this requires the researcher to strive for the success of the research group as opposed to only their own individual success and development.

Communication & Dissemination Skills

Criteria	Description
Variation of communication platforms used	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have experience using multiple different platforms when communicating and/or disseminating research. ➤ Variation in communication platforms which also target different audiences is desirable. ➤ Here it is important to see that researchers are familiar with different forms of dissemination platforms and when to utilize them. ➤ Knowledge and use of platforms relevant to the business industry is especially important.
Variation of target audiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have experiences in communicating with or to a variation of audiences. ➤ Being able to verbally and non-verbally communicate with different industry official, policymakers, students and citizens is very valuable and supports open access of research and wider social impact opportunities. ➤ This also includes producing and adapting materials and speeches to relate to different audiences. ➤ Communication with a variation of business industry stakeholders is particularly important.
Variation of development project stakeholder and/or partner collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Researchers' ability to collaborate with various stakeholders or other partners demonstrates flexibility in working with different industries and being able to incorporate different ideas and needs. ➤ A prioritisation is given to experience in/with the business industry.

Teamwork and Collaboration Skills

Criteria	Description
Variation of development project, stakeholder and/or partner collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Researchers' ability to collaborate with various stakeholders or other partners demonstrates flexibility in working with different industries and being able to incorporate different ideas and needs. ➤ Prioritization is given to experience in/with the business industry.
Demonstrated teamwork experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for researchers to have experience in teamwork. ➤ Teamwork experience in other professions and roles outside of research and/or development projects are also acknowledged.

Ideal Research Proposal

Creativity	
Criteria	Description
<p>Ability to envision new possibilities and ideas</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable to see that researchers are interested and motivated in conducting innovative research and open to ‘outside of the box’ ideas. ➤ This skill can be examined by discussing current and or previous research or development projects and what motivated them to conduct the research or why they thought their research was relevant. ➤ This skill can also be examined by discussing what the researchers’ ideal research or development project proposal would be.
<p>Willingness to try new approaches</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable to see that researchers are interested and motivated in conducting innovative research and open to ‘outside of the box’ ideas and try new ideas. ➤ This skill can be examined by discussing current and previous research or development projects and to what extent new approaches (ideas, tools, theories, stakeholders etc.) were incorporated. ➤ This skill can also be examined by discussing the researchers’ ideal research or development project proposal.
<p>Open to taking calculated risks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is desirable to see that researchers can take calculated risks when exploring or attempting new innovative research or development projects. ➤ This can be examined by discussing current or previous research or development projects and how they considered the practicality and feasibility of these. ➤ This can also be examined when discussing the researchers’ ideal research or development project proposal and to what extent their ideal proposal considers feasibility, practicality, reliability etc.

Tenure Track Evaluation Process

1st Evaluation

The 1st tenure track evaluation will be conducted by the supervisor of the Principal Research Scientist after they have been employed for around 4 months. The purpose of the 1st evaluation is to get an understanding of the PRS's current experience, strengths, weaknesses and development needs. The 1st evaluation provides a foundation and development strategy on which the rest of the tenure track process and evaluation are based upon. As the PRS is also heading towards the end of their probation period, the end of probation discussion will also be conducted during this evaluation.

The following tools will be used:

➤ **RUN EU PLUS- Self-assessment**

- Researchers will need to conduct a self-assessment using the online RUN EU PLUS tool. The results of the self-assessment will be discussed with the supervisor. Needed career development support will be arranged accordingly.

➤ **Research Plan Assessment and Overview**

- The PRS and their supervisor will complete an overview of the PRS's research plan and conduct a clear strategy for the rest of the tenure track process. Needed career development support will be arranged accordingly.

➤ **Competence Web Diagrams**

- A web diagram will be created for each PRS plotting their current competence levels at the 1st evaluation stage. Needed career development support will be arranged accordingly.

➤ **End of Tenure Track Evaluation Template**

- The final tenure track evaluation will be used to provide guidance on which skills, competencies and goals need to be achieved by the PRS during the tenure track process. Needed career development support will be arranged accordingly.

➤ **End of Probation Discussion**

- The PRS and their respective supervisor, will conduct a standard end of probation discussion, where both the supervisor and the PRS can express any concerns or issues regarding employment.

2nd Evaluation

The 2nd tenure track evaluation will be conducted by the supervisor of the Principal Research Scientist during months 18-21 of starting the tenure track process.

The purpose of the 2nd evaluation is to assess the progress of the PRS and identify any further support needed. During the 2nd evaluation a member from the tenure track evaluation team will assist in conducting a preliminary end of tenure track evaluation of the PRS and provide feedback on the areas needing further development.

In the 2nd tenure track evaluation, the following tools will be used:

➤ **RUN EU PLUS- Self-assessment**

- The PRS will need to conduct a self-assessment using the online RUN EU PLUS tool. The results of the self-assessment will be **compared to the results of the 1st tenure track evaluation** and discussed with the supervisor. Needed career development support will be arranged accordingly.

➤ **Research Plan Assessment and Overview**

- The PRS and their supervisor will complete an overview of the PRS's research plan and conduct a clear strategy for the rest of the tenure track process. Needed career development support will be arranged accordingly.

➤ **Competence Web Diagrams**

- A web diagram will be created for their current competence levels at the 2nd evaluation stage. Progress made from the 1st evaluation will be noted. Needed career development support will be arranged accordingly.

➤ **End of Tenure Track Evaluation Template**

- The final tenure track evaluation will be used to provide guidance on which skills, competencies and goals need to be achieved by the PRS during the tenure track process. Needed career development support will be arranged accordingly.

The same elements and process to the 1st evaluation will be followed. The results of the 1st evaluation and the goals and objectives set in the 1st evaluation will be reviewed in the 2nd evaluation. **Progress, development and strong motivation and initiative will be evaluated.** It is important to set new goals, objectives and development needs for the PRS, so they will be equipped to perform well in the final tenure track evaluation.

3rd Evaluation

The purpose of the 3rd evaluation is to assess the progress and development of the PRS over the tenure track period and evaluate the overall competence of the PRS. During the 3rd evaluation the researcher evaluation team will be responsible for conducting the assessment and will have access to all the evaluation results and materials from the 1st and 2nd evaluation.

In the 3rd tenure track evaluation, the following tools will be used:

➤ **RUN EU PLUS- Self-assessment**

- The PRS will need to conduct a self-assessment using the online RUN EU PLUS tool. The results of the self-assessment will be **compared to the results of the 1st and 2nd tenure track evaluation**. The evaluation team and the supervisor will discuss these results.

➤ **Research Plan**

- The evaluation team will look at the progress of the proposed research. The goals and objectives set will be looked at and grounded justification for any incompleteness, delays or alterations in the research strategy will be recognized also.

➤ **TENK CV**

- The PRS will update their TENK CV. Additions in experience from the start of the tenure track will be highlighted. The researcher evaluation team should assess the progress made since the start of the tenure track process and not at the entire TENK CV itself.

➤ **List of Publications**

- The PRS will update their List of Publications. Additions in publications from the start of the tenure track will be highlighted. The researcher evaluation team should assess the progress made in the List of Publications since the start of the tenure track process and not at the entire List of Publications itself.

➤ **Competence Web Diagrams**

- A web diagram will be created for the PRS's current competence levels at the 3rd stage evaluation. Progress made since the 1st and 2nd evaluation will be recognized.

Tenure Track Tools

RUN EU PLUS Self-Assessment

The self-assessment can be accessed through the following link: [Cloud Of Knowledge](#)

The RUN EU PLUS Self-Assessment allows researchers to conduct a self-assessment of their researcher skills and experiences, print and share the results with their respective supervisors, and conduct and compare follow up assessments.

The script for the self-assessment can be found in Annex

Research Plan Assessment and Overview

Effective Completion of Research

At HAMK the utilisation of the criteria below, will most likely occur during the tenure track evaluation process. However, the below mentioned criteria can also be applied and identified when examining previous or proposed research.

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
Objectives and aims achieved or shortcoming acknowledged	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss which objectives and aims will be achieved, when, how and measured through which tools and methods. ➤ Principal research scientists should have a clear plan for how they will achieve their objectives and aims. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the progress made on objectives and aims. ➤ Identify any challenges and shortcomings. ➤ Create a new strategy for achieving aims and objectives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess the completion and achievement of the set out aims and objectives. ➤ Grounded justification for any shortcomings also needs to be recognised.
Time management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Plan an initial timeline to conduct the research. ➤ Make timely expectations for the following evaluation. ➤ It is important to consider which aspects of the project may cause delays and respond to these effectively. ➤ Principal research scientists should have a clear timetable and plan for the research. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the progress made regarding the originally planned timeline. ➤ Make amendments to this timeline as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent project has been completed in accordance with the timeline. ➤ Grounded justification for any shortcomings also needs to be recognised.
Ability to recognize appropriate tools, theoretical frameworks, analysis methods etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the proposed tools and methods which will be utilised in the project. ➤ The PRS should have a clear justification for choosing these specific tools and methods and be also aware of their potential limitations, challenges and alternatives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the continued appropriateness and relevance of the tools and methods chosen. ➤ Make amendments as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess the justification of the chosen tools and methods. ➤ Grounded justification and lessons learnt for choosing inappropriate tools and methods needs to be recognised.
Consideration and recognition for research ethics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the potential research ethical violations which may occur or need to be considered. ➤ The PRS should have a clear understanding of how the research will be conducted ethically and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the identified research ethical considerations. ➤ Discuss any amendments or changes which need to be made. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent research ethics were identified and followed. ➤ Lessons learnt also needs to be recognised.

	be able to justify any potential ethical limitations .		
Consideration of regional, national, and/or international strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the extent to which regional, national and/or international strategies and/or objectives have been or could be incorporated into the research. ➤ A clear plan and objectives should be set for this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the regional, national and/or international strategies have been or will be incorporated. ➤ Make amendments as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the plan on incorporating regional, national, and/or international strategies has been followed. ➤ Lessons learnt also needs to be recognised.
Consideration of integration with education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the extent to which HAMK study units and courses will be or could be incorporated into the research. ➤ A clear plan and objectives should be set for this. A plan for collaboration with lecturers or study units should be defined. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the plan on incorporating education has been or will be followed. ➤ Make amendments as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the plan on incorporating education has been followed successfully. ➤ Justified shortcomings and lessons learnt need to be recognised.
Justification of discrepancies and/or changes in agreed upon research plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss potential fallbacks, challenges, limitations etc. which may need to be considered. ➤ Principal research scientists should have a clear understanding of potential fallbacks in the research and be able to deviate from original plan with coherent justification. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the amendments and changes that needed to be made and ensure there is grounded justification and recognition of these. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess how amendments, changes, and shortcomings have been acknowledged and reacted upon by the PRS.

Adoption of Open Science Practices

At HAMK the utilisation of the criteria below, will most likely occur during the tenure track evaluation process. However, the below mentioned criteria can also be applied and identified when examining previous or proposed research.

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
Open access publication and research dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss or identify open access journals, research platforms, and channels which would support open public access. ➤ Discuss the options with the principal research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the progress made in publishing open access. ➤ Make amendments and new plans as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent open access publishing has been attempted. ➤ Grounded justification for not publishing open access needs

	<p>scientist, if HAMK has any affiliations with directories especially in the applied field which would allow open access, whilst also avoiding the publishers APC charge.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Identify the most relevant options. ➤ Principal Research Scientists should understand which open access journals and platforms they should target when disseminating research. ➤ Able to justify the use of non-open access research dissemination. 		to also be recognized.
Open data sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the potential of sharing data. ➤ Identify which data is sharable and which needs to remain confidential. ➤ Principal Research Scientists should consider which aspects of the data can be shared, how and when. ➤ Which aspects need to remain confidential and be able to justify this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the current plan for open data sharing. ➤ Make amendments to the plan as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the open data sharing plan. ➤ Grounded justification for sharing and/or not sharing data should be recognized.
Open methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the potential of sharing methods used. ➤ Identify if there are methods which need to remain confidential. ➤ Principal Research Scientists should consider which methods can be shared, how and when. ➤ Which aspects need to remain confidential and be able to justify this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the current plan for open methods. ➤ Make amendments to the plan as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the open methods plan. ➤ Grounded justification for using and/or not using open methods should be recognized.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss how research can be accessible to society members, organization, businesses etc. ➤ Which events and dissemination platforms can be used and when. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the research and the outputs have been disseminated openly and in consideration of reaching society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent sharing of the research and its results etc. have been actively disseminated in a manner which supports accessibility

<p>Sharing with society members and businesses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ How does the communication style need to be altered for different audiences. ➤ Principal Research Scientists should understand how the research can be disseminated to reach societal members. ➤ Understanding of how communication needs to be conducted for societal members. 	<p>members and the business industry.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Make amendments to the plan or create new objectives and/or strategies. 	<p>to society members and the business industry.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the original plan has been followed and considered.
<p>Open educational resources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the relevance of creating educational materials from the research. ➤ Discuss how these would be made open access. ➤ Principal Research Scientists should understand if the creation of educational materials can be incorporated into the research. ➤ How can these materials be made accessible and free and through which platforms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the plan for creating open educational resources from the research has been considered. ➤ Make amendments to the plan as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent this plan has been followed and considered.

Competence Web Diagrams

Networking Skills

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
<p>Extent of existing networks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the PRS's existing networks in the business industry, academic institutions, government and civil society. ➤ Prioritization of business industry networks. ➤ These can be enhanced by outreaching relevant representatives in these networks, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the objectives for increasing relevant networks have been successful. ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has been active in this outreach. ➤ Make new plans and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess the growth and expansion of new relevant networks during the tenure track period. ➤ Assess the extent of outreach done by the PRS to increase these networks. ➤ Consider to what extent the plan and objectives set by the PRS and their supervisor have been followed.

	<p>joining events, inviting representatives to relevant events and active collaboration.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Make clear objectives for expanding the researchers' current networks. 		
<p>Experience in networking roles</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the PRS's experience in networking. ➤ Discuss their experience in networking with a range of stakeholders from the business industry, academic institutions, government and civil society. ➤ Prioritization of business industry networking experience. ➤ PRS should actively enhance their networking experience, especially within the business industry. ➤ Make clear objectives for the PRS to enhance their networking experience. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the networking experience of the PRS has enhanced. ➤ To what extent has the PRS achieved the objectives and plan set out in the 1st evaluation. ➤ Make new plans and objectives for the remaining tenure track period. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS had gained further networking experience during the tenure track period. ➤ Assess to what extent the plan and objectives set out for increasing networking experience has been followed.
<p>Experience in face-to-face networking</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the PRS's experience in face-to-face networking. ➤ Networking skills through different forms and platforms are desirable but face-to-face networking is important. ➤ Face-to-face networking experience can be improved by attending live conferences and events, scheduling face-to-face meetings with stakeholders etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has gained more face-to-face experience in networking. ➤ Examine to what extent the plans and objectives set in the 1st evaluation have been followed. ➤ Make new plans and objectives as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS had gained further face-to-face networking experience during the tenure track period. ➤ Assess to what extent the plan and objectives set out have been followed and considered.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Make clear objectives for the PRS to enhance their face-to-face networking experience. 		
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Leadership Skills and Experience

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
Experience in leadership roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the PRS's experience in leadership, in research team leadership. ➤ PRS should understand what type of leadership is expected from them and what their role as a leader is. ➤ The PRS should have a clear understanding and a plan on how to enhance their skills as research team leaders. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has gained experience in leadership. ➤ Examine to what extent PRS has enhanced their skills and the plan set out in the 1st evaluation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has enhanced their leadership skills during the tenure track period. ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS had followed the plan and objectives set out for them.
Demonstrates similar leadership values and understanding of duties as organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the PRS's understanding of their role and responsibilities as a leader in the research team. ➤ The PRS should have a clear understanding of the leadership values which are expected of them. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has been able to demonstrate and follow the leadership values of HAMK. ➤ Assess if there still is a need for support. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has been able to demonstrate the values of HAMK in leadership. ➤ How do their research team view them as research leaders? ➤ Has the PRS found support for enhancing their leadership skills? ➤ Peer review is an important factor.

Communication & Dissemination Skills

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the experience the PRS has in disseminating research results and outputs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has disseminated information about the research and the variety 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has attempted to disseminate the research and outputs.

<p>Extent of research dissemination</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Desirable for PRS to know how to disseminate research results through different platforms and to different audiences. ➤ The PRS should attempt to utilise different platforms, mediums and audiences when disseminating research results. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<p>of platforms and methods already utilised.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Make plans and objectives for further dissemination. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ To what extent have they followed and considered the objectives and plan set.
<p>Variation of communication platforms used</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ PRS should try to expand their use of different platforms. ➤ PRS should be able to identify appropriate platforms and be able to adapt their communication respectively. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has used different communication platforms and understood their importance and relevance. ➤ Examine to what extent they still plan on using different platforms. ➤ Make new objectives and plans as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has used different communication platforms and adapted communication style accordingly. ➤ Assess to what extent the plan and objectives have been followed and considered.
<p>Variation of target audiences</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ PRS should try to expand their communication to different audiences. ➤ This includes being able to identify the correct dissemination platforms, the appropriate mediums used, and the appropriate language used. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has targeted different audiences. ➤ Consider how they continue to do this during the rest of the tenure track period. ➤ Consider their justification for reaching out to certain audiences only. ➤ Make new plans and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has attempted to target different audiences during the tenure track period. ➤ Assess to what extent the objectives and plans set out have been followed and considered.
<p>Open access</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ PRS should have an understanding on how to promote open access of their research dissemination. ➤ Knowing which journals, methods and tools to consider. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent open access and dissemination have been considered. ➤ Consider grounded justification for not being able to utilise this, ➤ Make further plans and objectives as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent open access to research information and results has been considered. ➤ To what extent have plans and objectives been followed. ➤ Grounded justification for not using open access need to be recognized.

<p>Preparation of marketing and pitching material</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent PRS has experience marketing research ideas and preparing appropriate materials. ➤ PRS should expand their skills in being able to market their research ideas to the business industry. ➤ This includes being able to produce coherent materials which uses industry relevant language. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent has the PRS gained experience and increased their skills in producing marketing materials for their research. ➤ make new plans and objectives as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent has the PRS gained further experience and skills in marketing material preparation during the tenure track period. ➤ To what extent has the plan and objectives been followed.
<p>Extent of face-to-face stakeholder interaction.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the PRS's experience in face-to-face communication with stakeholders. ➤ Face-to-face communication skills can be improved by attending live conferences and events, scheduling face-to-face meetings with stakeholders etc. ➤ Make clear objectives for the PRS to enhance their face-to-face communication experience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent has the PRS gained experience in face-to-face interaction and communication with stakeholders. ➤ Identify needed development and support. ➤ Make new plans and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent has the PRS gained the needed experience for face-to-face interaction during the tenure track period. ➤ To what extent has the PRS followed the plan and objectives set. ➤ Grounded justification for failing to meet the demands needs to be considered. ➤ Attempts need to be acknowledged.

Publishing

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
<p>Variation of role in authorship (1st author, 2nd author, etc.)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent PRS have experience in different authorship roles in collaborations. ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on expanding their range of authorship roles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the progress made by the PRS in expanding their publication role experience. ➤ Make new objectives and plans as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has considered and followed the plans set out. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to expand on different authorship role experience needs to be recognised.

<p>Open access publishing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ PRS should have an understanding on how to promote open access of their research dissemination. ➤ Knowing which journals, methods and tools to consider. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent open access publishing has been attempted. ➤ Make new plans and objectives as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has followed plans and objectives set. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered. ➤ Attempts need to be considered.
<p>Variation in transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary and specialization of published research</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent PRS has experience conducting transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary publishing. ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on conducting research and publishing through a transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent PRS has been able to accomplish transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary publishing targets. ➤ Consider challenges and make new plans and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has followed the plans and objectives set out. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered. ➤ Attempts need to be considered.
<p>Variation of publication collaborations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has experience in collaborating and publishing with different researchers. ➤ The PRS should have a clear plan on expanding their collaboration with different groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has been able to or has attempted to collaborate with different researchers. ➤ Make new objectives and plans as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has followed the plans and objectives set out. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered. ➤ Attempts need to be considered.
<p>Variation of both sole authorship and multiple authorship publications</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has experience in publishing both sole and in authorship groups. ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on expanding both their sole and multiple authorship publications. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has been able to or has attempted to enhance their experience in multiple and/or sole authorship experience. ➤ Make new objectives and plans as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has followed the plans and objectives set out. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has been able 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has followed the

<p>Collaboration within international authorship groups</p>	<p>experience in publishing with international authors, researchers etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on expanding their experience in working with international researchers. 	<p>to or has attempted to collaborate with researchers from international backgrounds.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Make new objectives and plans as needed. 	<p>plans and objectives set out.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.
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Pedagogical Skills

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
<p>Experience collaborating with educational professionals, lecturers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent PRS has experience in collaborating with educators and developing study units. ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on how they can collaborate with lecturers and educators at HAMK. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has achieved the set-out plans and objectives and/or sets out to do this. ➤ Make plans, objectives and identify support needs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has followed the plans and objectives set out. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered. ➤ Attempts need to be considered.
<p>Integrating study units into research and/or development projects</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent PRS has experience in integrating research with study units and courses. ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on how to integrate their proposed research with HAMK study units and/or courses. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has achieved the set-out plans and objectives and/or sets out to do this. ➤ Make plans, objectives and identify support needs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has followed the plans and objectives set out. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered. ➤ Attempts need to be considered.
<p>Experience in teaching activities and/roles</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has teaching experience especially at the UAS level. ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on enhancing their experience in teaching at HAMK. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has achieved the set-out plans and objectives and/or sets out to do this. ➤ Make plans, objectives and identify support needs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has followed the plans and objectives set out. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.

➤ **HAMK 100** could help to support this.

➤ **Attempts** need to be considered.

Teamwork and Collaboration Skills

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
Variation of stakeholder collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the PRS experience with working and collaborating with different stakeholders. ➤ The variation of stakeholders is important. Stakeholders from the business industry, academic institutions, government and civil society should be expanded. ➤ Business industry stakeholders are prioritized. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has been able to increase the variation of stakeholders they are collaborating with. ➤ Business industry stakeholders should be prioritized. ➤ Make new plans and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has been able to or has attempted to expand their collaboration with different stakeholders. ➤ To what extent has PRS followed or considered the plans and objectives set. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.
Variation in authorship collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has experience in collaborating and publishing with different researchers. ➤ The PRS should have a clear plan on expanding their collaboration with different groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has experience in collaborating and publishing with different researchers. ➤ The PRS should have a clear plan on expanding their collaboration with different groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has been able to or has attempted to collaborate with different researchers. ➤ Make new objectives and plans as needed. ➤ Attempts need to be considered
Demonstrated experience in research teams	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the PRS's experience in teamwork, in particular research team teamwork. ➤ PRS should understand what type of teamwork is expected from research teams at HAMK. ➤ The PRS should have a clear understanding and a plan on how to enhance their skills in research team teamwork. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has been able to familiarize with teamwork values at HAMK. ➤ To what extent do they work well within the research team. ➤ Make new plans and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has followed and considered the plans and objectives set. ➤ Assess how well they have performed as a team member in the research team. ➤ Peer review is an important factor.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 		
Variation of funding application collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has experience in collaborating with different peers in funding applications. ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on expanding their variation of funding application collaborations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has increased their experience in collaborating in different funding applications. ➤ Make new plans and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has followed the plans and objectives et. ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has increased their collaboration experience in funding applications during the tenure track period. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.

Peer Development

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
Experience in peer mentoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent PRS has experience in mentoring peers and helping develop skills and specialization of research team. ➤ PRS should understand that mentoring and supporting peers in the research team is expected at HAMK. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent PRS has been able to further enhance their mentoring skills or had mentoring opportunities. ➤ Make new plans and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has followed the plans and objectives which have been set. ➤ Peer review is an important factor in this.
Peer review experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent PRS has experience in providing reviews on peer publications, funding applications etc. ➤ Discuss how the PRS can gain more experience in peer review activities and roles. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent PRS has enhanced their peer review skills or gained peer review experience. ➤ Make new plans and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has followed and considered the plans and objectives set. ➤ To what extent has PRS attempted to enhance skills and experience.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent PRS has experience in providing constructive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent PRS has enhanced their peer feedback 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has followed and

<p>Peer feedback experience</p>	<p>and reflective feedback on peer performance, especially in teamwork and collaborations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<p>skills or gained peer feedback experience.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Make new plans and objectives. 	<p>considered the plans and objectives set.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ To what extent has PRS attempted to enhance skills and experience.
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Funding Applications

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
<p>Activeness in funding application process</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on submitting funding applications. ➤ Set appropriate objectives and aims. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has reached the objectives and aims set. ➤ Make new objectives as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has been active in applying for funding. ➤ To what extent has the PRS followed the plans and aims set.
<p>Variation of role</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Concerning the funding application process, discuss how much experience the PRS has in different roles. ➤ The PRS should have a clear plan on how to expand their experience in different funding application roles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has been able to gain experience in different funding application roles. ➤ Make new plans and objectives as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has followed and considered the plans and objectives set. ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has increased their experience in different roles in the funding application process during the tenure track process. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.
<p>Variation of funding sources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss with the PRS how much experience they have in applying to different funding sources. ➤ The PRS should have a clear plan on how to expand their experience in applying for different types of funding from different funding sources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has increased the variation of funding sources applied to. ➤ Make new plans and objectives as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has followed and considered the plans and objectives set. ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has increased their experience in applying to different funding sources during the tenure track process. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet

			plans and objectives needs to be considered.
Variation of funding application collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has experience in collaborating with different peers in funding applications. ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on expanding their variation of funding application collaborations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has increased their experience in collaborating in different funding applications. ➤ Make new plans and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has followed the plans and objectives et. ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has increased their collaboration experience in funding applications during the tenure track period. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.

Entrepreneurship Skills

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
Leadership experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ This can be discussed in connection to the PRS's leadership skills and experience. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess the overview of leadership criteria of the PRS. ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has been able to enhance their leadership skills as this also reflects the skills in entrepreneurship. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess the progress made in the leadership criteria category.
Communication experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ This can be discussed in connection to the PRS's communication skills and experience. ➤ Most important: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ability to communicate effectively and adapt their communication style to different audiences. - communicate face-to-face. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess the overview of communication criteria of PRS. ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has been able to enhance their communication skills in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ability to communicate effectively and adapt their communication style to different audiences. - communicate face-to-face. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess the progress made in the communication criteria category. ➤ In particular: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ability to communicate effectively and adapt their communication style to different audiences. - communicate face-to-face.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ This also reflects the skills in entrepreneurship. 	
Problem-solving experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss with the PRS their experience in providing practical solutions to stakeholders. ➤ To what extent have stakeholders adopted project recommendations and/or developed solutions. ➤ To what extent have stakeholders actively benefitted from projects the PRS has been involved in. ➤ Discuss how the PRS plans to react to challenges, to what extent they can predict these etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent stakeholders in the research and/or project will benefit from the research. ➤ To what extent are the stakeholders likely to adopt the solutions, recommendations and/or project outputs. ➤ How has the PRS reacted to challenges, delays or issues in regard to the time management and/or finances of the research. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess the impact of the research on the stakeholders. ➤ Has the PRS research resolved the problems of the stakeholder or provided solutions. ➤ Have the stakeholders decided to adopt the research output? ➤ Stakeholder feedback will be an important factor. ➤ To what extent has PRS been successful in dealing with challenges, delays or other issues in the project?
Adaptability and Flexibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent PRS has experience in collaborating with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - different researchers, - different stakeholders, - funding application groups, - Different disciplines and research fields ➤ Consider the overview of the teamwork criteria. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the success of the PRS in collaborating with different stakeholders, researchers, funding application groups, and with different disciplines and research fields. ➤ Consider the overview of the teamwork criteria. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Peer review and/or feedback and stakeholder feedback will be important factors. ➤ How successful has the PRS been in working well. ➤ Consider the overview of the teamwork criteria.
Financial literacy experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent PRS has experience in financially managing and monitoring project expenditure. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has been able to gain further understanding and skill in financial literacy experience. ➤ Their own financial management of their research and/or courses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has been successful in financially managing their research and/or project. ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has seemed support in areas needing development.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ This can be discussed in relation to the PRS's proposed research plan and respective 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has been able to implement the project and/or research in the projected time. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has been able to implement project and/or

<p>Time management experience</p>	<p>time management of the research.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ To what extent is the PRS able to consider potential delays, fallbacks etc. ➤ How realistic is the PRS's proposed timeline for the project. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ To what extent has the PRS been able to successfully manage delays in schedule etc. 	<p>research in projected timeline.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Grounded justification for delays and appropriate reactions to these delays and challenges needs to also be recognized.
<p>Risk-taking</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ This can be discussed in relation to the PRS's proposed research plan. ➤ To what extent is the PRS able to practice innovative thinking alongside consideration for calculated risk. ➤ To what extent is the PRS able to justify their research approach. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess the progress of the research and/or project. ➤ How have they reacted to unforeseen circumstances? ➤ Is their approach innovative and ambitious? ➤ Make plans and objectives as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess the progress of the research and/or project. ➤ How have they reacted to unforeseen circumstances? ➤ Is their approach innovative and ambitious?
<p>Strategic planning</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ This can be discussed in relation to the PRS's proposed research plan. ➤ To what extent is PRS able to consider potential delays, challenges, fallbacks and plan for this respectively. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess the progress of the research and/or project. ➤ Has there been unforeseen issues and/or circumstances which have impacted the research and/or project? ➤ Is the PRS able to make other justified plans for the next duration of the tenure track. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has been able to plan around and prepare for challenges and issues in the project. ➤ To what extent has the PRS been able to react to unforeseen issues and even take advantage of these.

End of Tenure Track Evaluation

Effective Completion of Research Proposal

In the first evaluation the supervisor should go through the final tenure track evaluation with the PRS so they understand what will be evaluated by the end of the tenure track process.

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss which objectives and aims will be achieved, when, how and measured through 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the progress made on objectives and aims. ➤ Identify any challenges and shortcomings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess the completion and achievement of the set out aims and objectives.

<p>Objectives and aims achieved or shortcoming acknowledged</p>	<p>which tools and methods.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Principal research scientists should have a clear plan for how they will achieve their objectives and aims. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Create a new strategy for achieving aims and objectives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Grounded justification for any shortcomings also needs to be recognised.
<p>Time management</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Plan an initial timeline to conduct the research. ➤ Make timely expectations for the following evaluation. ➤ It is important to consider which aspects of the project may cause delays and respond to these effectively. ➤ Principal research scientists should have a clear timetable and plan for the research. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the progress made regarding the originally planned timeline. ➤ Make amendments to this timeline as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent project has been completed in accordance with the timeline. ➤ Grounded justification for any shortcomings also needs to be recognised.
<p>Consideration and recognition for research ethics</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the potential research ethical violations which may occur or need to be considered. ➤ The PRS should have a clear understanding of how the research will be conducted ethically and be able to justify any potential ethical limitations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the identified research ethical considerations. ➤ Discuss any amendments or changes which need to be made. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent research ethics were identified and followed. ➤ Lessons learnt also needs to be recognised.
<p>Consideration of regional, national, and/or international strategies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the extent to which regional, national and/or international strategies and/or objectives have been or could be incorporated into the research. ➤ A clear plan and objectives should be set for this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the regional, national and/or international strategies have been or will be incorporated. ➤ Make amendments as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the plan on incorporating regional, national, and/or international strategies has been followed. ➤ Lessons learnt also needs to be recognised.
<p>Consideration of integration with education</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the extent to which HAMK study units and courses will be or could be incorporated into the research. ➤ A clear plan and objectives should be set for this. A plan for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the plan on incorporating education has been or will be followed. ➤ Make amendments as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the plan on incorporating education has been followed successfully. ➤ Justified shortcomings and

	collaboration with lecturers or study units should be defined.		lessons learnt need to be recognised .
Added value or benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Set out clear understandings for the added value of the research. ➤ What benefit, innovation or other value can the research outputs, the research approach, the research stakeholders, provide. ➤ Set out clear plans and objectives for the PRS to ensure that the research produced added value and/or benefit. ➤ Consider how the added benefit and/or value can be captured. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine how the attainment of the added value and/or benefit of the research and/or project is progressing. ➤ Consider alternative benefits and/or values which could be attained. ➤ Make plans and objectives as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the research and/or project has achieved added value and/or benefit. ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has followed the plans and guides for this.

Business Industry Collaboration

The enhancement in business industry collaboration over the tenure track process will be examined.

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
Activeness in the business industry of stakeholder networking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has networked with business industry stakeholders. ➤ Identify relevant networks and networking opportunities. ➤ Make objectives and aims for the PRS. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent PRS has been active in exploring and attending relevant networks and networking opportunities. ➤ Make new objectives and aims as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has been successful in enhancing their activeness in business industry stakeholder networking. ➤ To what extent has the PRS been successful in meeting the set objectives and aims. ➤ Grounded justification for any shortcomings also needs to be recognised.
Extent of business industry stakeholder inclusion in research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent PRS has considered including business relevant stakeholders in the research. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has been successful in including the stakeholders in the research. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has followed and successfully included

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Identify the extent to which these stakeholders can be included and ensure they are involved as possible. ➤ Make clear objectives and aims. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Identify to what extent this can be improved and make new aims and objectives. 	<p>the stakeholders in their research.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Grounded justification for any shortcomings also needs to be recognised.
<p>Added value and/or benefit of research to business industry stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has considered how the 'benefit' and 'value' of the research can be measured by business industry stakeholders. ➤ Will this be done via feedback and reviews? ➤ Will the stakeholder be asked to adopt new methods, processes etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has considered how to ensure the business stakeholders benefit can be measured and accounted for. ➤ Make new objectives and aims as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has been successful in creating added value or benefit to stakeholders. ➤ Recognized 'improvements needed' and or 'lessons learnt' should be acknowledged. ➤ Important to assess to what extent PRS has tried to secure and consider stakeholder value and benefit and been active in measuring this.
<p>Variation in communication with business industry stakeholders (esp. face-to-face)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the PRS current experience in face-to-face networking with business industry stakeholders and if they need to enhance their skills and experience. ➤ Make objectives and aims. ➤ Identify potential and relevant networking events and/or opportunities to engage with stakeholders at live meetings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has actively attended networking events. ➤ Make new objectives and aims accordingly. ➤ Potentially identify further face-to-face networking opportunities and events as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has been active in securing the outlined objectives and aims. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.

Funding Applications

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
<p>Activeness in funding application process</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on submitting funding applications. ➤ Set appropriate objectives and aims. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has reached the objectives and aims set. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has been active in applying for funding.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Make new objectives as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ To what extent has the PRS followed the plans and aims set.
Variation of role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Concerning the funding application process, discuss how much experience the PRS has in different roles. ➤ The PRS should have a clear plan on how to expand their experience in different funding application roles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has been able to gain experience in different funding application roles. ➤ Make new plans and objectives as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has followed and considered the plans and objectives set. ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has increased their experience in different roles in the funding application process during the tenure track process. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.
Variation of funding sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss with the PRS how much experience they have in applying to different funding sources. ➤ The PRS should have a clear plan on how to expand their experience in applying for different types of funding from different funding sources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has increased the variation of funding sources applied to. ➤ Make new plans and objectives as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has followed and considered the plans and objectives set. ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has increased their experience in applying to different funding sources during the tenure track process. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.
Variation of funding application collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has experience in collaborating with different peers in funding applications. ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on expanding their variation of funding application collaborations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has increased their experience in collaborating in different funding applications. ➤ Make new plans and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has followed the plans and objectives et. ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has increased their collaboration experience in funding applications during the tenure track period.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.
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Networking Skills

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
Extent of existing networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the PRS's existing networks and to what extent the PRS should actively engage in new networks and networking events. ➤ Make objectives and aims. ➤ Identify potential and relevant networks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has actively engaged and/or contacted the networks identified. ➤ Make new objectives and aims accordingly. ➤ Potentially identify further networks and networking opportunities as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has been active in securing the outlined objectives and aims. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.
Experience in networking roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the PRS current experience in networking and if they need to enhance their skills and experience. ➤ Make objectives and aims. ➤ Identify potential and relevant networking events. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has actively attended networking events. ➤ Make new objectives and aims accordingly. ➤ Potentially identify further networking opportunities and events as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has been active in securing the outlined objectives and aims. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.
Experience in face-to-face networking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the PRS current experience in face-to-face networking and if they need to enhance their skills and experience. ➤ Make objectives and aims. ➤ Identify potential and relevant networking events and/or opportunities to engage with stakeholders at live meetings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has actively attended networking events. ➤ Make new objectives and aims accordingly. ➤ Potentially identify further face-to-face networking opportunities and events as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has been active in securing the outlined objectives and aims. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.

RDI Leadership

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
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<p>Demonstrates similar leadership values and understanding of duties as organization</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the PRS's understanding of their role and responsibilities as a leader in the research team. ➤ The PRS should have a clear understanding of the leadership values which are expected of them. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has been able to demonstrate and follow the leadership values of HAMK. Assess if there still is a need for support. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has been able to demonstrate the values of HAMK in leadership. ➤ How do their research team view them as research leaders? ➤ Has the PRS found support for enhancing their leadership skills? Peer review is an important factor.
<p>Activeness of research team</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ PRS should understand their objectives of gathering a research group. ➤ PRS should have a plan on how the research group will approach completing funding applications, secure cooperation with stakeholders (esp. the business industry), implement projects, publish, present at conferences etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has succeeded in gathering a research group. ➤ To what extent has the research group been able to accomplish funding applications, cooperation with stakeholders, projects and publications, conferences etc. ➤ Make new objectives as needed. ➤ Justified grounds for delays or not achieving the objectives should be recognized. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent has the PRS been successful in assembling a research group. ➤ To what extent has the research group been active in stakeholder collaboration, funding applications, publications, conferences etc. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered

Pedagogical Development

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
<p>Collaboration with educational professionals, lecturers, etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS is planning on collaborating with lecturers and/or educational professionals. ➤ Discuss potential interested lecturers and/or relevant study programs at HAMK. ➤ Make objectives and goals for contacting and collaborating lecturers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent PRS has followed up and/or collaborated with the lecturers and educational professionals. ➤ Make new objectives and aims accordingly. ➤ Justified grounds for delays or not achieving the objectives should be recognized. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has achieved the objectives and goals set for them. ➤ Have they actively tried to collaborate with HAMK lecturers and/or study programs. ➤ Justified grounds for delays or not achieving the

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Research roundtable program would be a potential avenue to explore if this gets implemented. 		objectives should be recognized.
Integrating study units into research and/or development projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS is planning on utilizing and benefiting their research and/ or expertise with HAMK study programs and students. ➤ Discuss potential interested lecturers and/or relevant study programs at HAMK. ➤ Make objectives and goals for incorporating students and study programs into the research. ➤ Research roundtable program would be a potential avenue to explore if this gets implemented. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent PRS has been able to integrate their research and expertise into study programs and/or utilize students. ➤ Make new objectives and aims accordingly. ➤ Justified grounds for delays or not achieving the objectives should be recognized. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has achieved the objectives and goals set for them. ➤ Have they actively tried to incorporate students into their research? Tried to incorporate their research and/or expertise into study programs? ➤ Justified grounds for delays or not achieving the objectives should be recognized.

Supervision

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
Experience in supervision roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss the need for the PRS to increase their supervision skills and experience. ➤ Set objectives and goals depending on the PRS needs. ➤ HAMK 100 may be able to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has been successful in gaining more supervision experience and/or improved their skills. ➤ Make new objectives and aims accordingly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has been successful in completing the aims and objectives set. ➤ To what extent have they been active in enhancing the needed experience and skills? ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to expand on different authorship role experience needs to be recognised.

Publishing

Criteria	1 st Evaluation	2 nd Evaluation	3 rd Evaluation
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<p>Variation of role in authorship (1st author, 2nd author, etc.)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent PRS have experience in different authorship roles in collaborations. ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on expanding their range of authorship roles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine the progress made by the PRS in expanding their publication role experience. ➤ Make new objectives and plans as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has considered and followed the plans set out. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to expand on different authorship role experience needs to be recognised.
<p>Open access publishing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ PRS should have an understanding on how to promote open access of their research dissemination. ➤ Knowing which journals, methods and tools to consider. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent open access publishing has been attempted. ➤ Make new plans and objectives as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has followed plans and objectives set. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered. ➤ Attempts need to be considered.
<p>Variation in transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary and specialization of published research</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent PRS has experience conducting transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary publishing. ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on conducting research and publishing through a transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary. ➤ HAMK 100 could help to support this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent PRS has been able to accomplish transdisciplinary, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary publishing targets. ➤ Consider challenges and make new plans and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has followed the plans and objectives set out. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered. ➤ Attempts need to be considered.
<p>Variation of publication collaborations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has experience in collaborating and publishing with different researchers. ➤ The PRS should have a clear plan on expanding their collaboration with different groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has been able to or has attempted to collaborate with different researchers. ➤ Make new objectives and plans as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has followed the plans and objectives set out. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered. ➤ Attempts need to be considered.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has been able 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent PRS has

<p>Variation of both sole authorship and multiple authorship publications</p>	<p>experience in publishing both sole and in authorship groups.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on expanding both their sole and multiple authorship publications. 	<p>to or has attempted to enhance their experience in multiple and/or sole authorship experience.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Make new objectives and plans as needed. 	<p>followed the plans and objectives set out.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.
<p>Collaboration within international authorship groups</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Discuss to what extent the PRS has experience in collaborating with different peers in funding applications. ➤ PRS should have a clear plan on expanding their variation of funding application collaborations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Examine to what extent the PRS has increased their experience in collaborating in different funding applications. ➤ Make new plans and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has followed the plans and objectives et. ➤ Assess to what extent the PRS has increased their collaboration experience in funding applications during the tenure track period. ➤ Grounded justification for not being able to meet plans and objectives needs to be considered.

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